

TEMPERATURE DEPENDENT ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF MOLYBDENUM-DOPED VANADIUM COMPOSITE THIN FILMS ON METALLIC PLATES FOR FUEL CELL APPLICATIONS

H. Jung¹, J. Noh¹, H. Kim¹, S. Um^{1*}

¹ School of Mechanical Engineering, Hanyang University,
17 Haengdang-dong, Seongdong-gu, Seoul 133-791, South Korea

* Corresponding author (sukkeeum@hanyang.ac.kr)

Keywords: *fuel cells; metallic bipolar plates; sol-gel; vanadium oxide composite thin films; molybdenum doping; electrical properties*

1 Introduction

Polymer electrolyte fuel cells (PEFCs) have received considerable attention as a potentially alternative power source for an automotive application over recent years. However, there are still several technical challenging issues to be solved before commercialization of PEFCs for this vehicular application: performance and reliability. Among the performance issues of fuel cells, cold starting at subzero temperature is one of the major drawbacks of the low temperature fuel cell for long term reliability and guaranteed performance [1-3].

For the successful cold starting of a fuel cell engine, either internal or external heat supply must be made to overcome the formation of ice from water below the freezing point of water. Currently most fuel cell engines adopt an external heating system, e.g. heat generation by electrical resistance in a water reservoir of a cooling system [4]. However, this external heating device consumes enormous amounts of electrical energy to thaw out and warm up the frozen electrochemical engines to reach a normal operational state (e.g. 60–80°C), which deteriorates the performance of fuel cell engines.

An energy-efficient way of a heat supply method can be made by applying highly electrically resistive material at low temperatures onto the surface of key fuel cell components (e.g. bipolar plate) in a thin film form, which can relatively minimize the parasitic loss compared to external heating of coolants. In the low current density range (i.e. $\leq 300\text{mA/cm}^2$), this highly electrically resistive material should be able to produce sufficient amounts of heat energy by thermal dissipation in the

form of Joule heating. In contrast, the electrical resistance of this material should be significantly reduced in the mild temperature range (e.g. below room temperature) due to the continuously generated heat as a by-product of fuel cell reactions. Therefore, the resistive material should have an electrical resistance inversely proportional to the fuel cell temperature, which is the distinctive feature of a negative temperature coefficient material [5-6].

The present study applies molybdenum-doped vanadium oxide compounds as the negative temperature coefficient materials onto the surface of flat metallic bipolar plates [7-8]. Then, the applicability of the negative temperature coefficient materials as an internal heat source for a fuel cell vehicle at sub-freezing temperature is evaluated by investigating the composition, morphology, and temperature dependent electrical properties.

2 Experimental

The pure and impure vanadium oxide composite thin films have been prepared by an aqueous sol-gel method from vanadium alkoxide solution mixed with n-type doping materials (e.g. molybdenum) and then coated on the surface of a pre-cleaned 316L stainless steel bipolar plate with natural passive oxide layer. The vanadium oxide composite thin films with different mol % of Mo (0 to 4 mol %) to vanadium sol were deposited by dip-coating machine with pull rate from 1mm/s in this study. After dip-coating under ambient humidity condition, we obtained homogeneous vanadium oxide thin films with mostly transparent and pale yellow. The coated specimens were then dried around 80°C in air, which occurred to the color shift

Fig.1. Experimental process for the fabrication of vanadium composite thin films deposited on 316L stainless steel bipolar plates

to green due to the reduction of V^{5+} to V^{4+} ($\text{V}^{4+}/\text{V}^{5+} \approx 10\%$) [9-10]. Finally, the V_2O_5 dry film was annealed in a tubular chamber at 500°C which was programmed for temperature control and operated in a vacuum state of 10^{-3} torr. All the experimental processes are summarized in Fig. 1. After the post heat treatment process, we obtained molybdenum-doped vanadium composite thin films on metallic plates as shown in Fig. 2.

Subsequently, X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) were used to investigate the chemical compositions, crystalline phases, and microstructure of the molybdenum-doped vanadium oxide composite thin films, respectively. In addition, modulation effect of n-type doping material on the temperature dependent electrical resistance of the vanadium composite thin films was carefully observed over a temperature range from -20°C to 80°C .

3 Results & Discussion

As representative results of these experiments,

Fig.2. A sample of a molybdenum-doped vanadium composite thin films coated metallic plate

Fig. 3 represents the XRD spectrum of a 1mol % Mo-doped sample (SVM 1). There are strong V_2O_5 and V_2O_3 peaks indicating that this sample has not been fully reduced. The existence of a binary mixture of vanadium oxide phases is attributed to the reducing conditions induced by the partial pressure of oxygen in the post heat-treatment process. Most importantly, no peaks corresponding to molybdenum oxides are observed in Fig. 3, which implies that vanadium sites in vanadium oxides structure were successfully substituted by molybdenum as a dopant in the vanadium oxides. A minor peak for V_5S_4 is observed at $2\theta \approx 14^\circ$, indicating that a minute amount of sulfur in the flat metallic bipolar plates has combined with vanadium phases.

The most striking results from this study were that the variation of temperature dependent electrical properties for the three different samples. It is clearly seen that both SVM 1 (1mol% Mo-doped vanadium oxide composite thin film) and SVM 2 (2mol% Mo-doped vanadium oxide composite thin film) with the molybdenum demonstrate typical negative temperature coefficient characteristics with temperature and have electrical resistances greater than the minimum requirement of electrical resistance calculated in theoretical target value. We can infer from Fig. 4 that there will be no further increase in electrical resistance below -10°C and this makes it possible to expand the applicable temperature range of the experimental result to -20°C .

Moreover, the electrical resistances in both samples with the molybdenum dopant drop significantly at about 10°C and converge on an extremely small value similar to that of a flat

Fig.3. XRD pattern of a 1mol% Mo-doped sample

Fig.4. Measured electrical resistances as a function of temperature with various compositions of vanadium and molybdenum compounds. Dotted line indicates the required minimum electrical resistance for the cold starting of fuel cell

metallic bipolar plate without any surface treatment at higher temperatures, i.e. $T \geq 50^\circ\text{C}$.

Therefore, we can expect that vanadium oxides doped with molybdenum can be substantially utilized for the cold starting of polymer electrolyte fuel cells which requires considerable thermal sources for ice-melting at sub-zero temperatures. Particularly, this internal heating method does not require any external heat-supply equipments for cold starting of fuel cell vehicles as well as control logic to adjust the amount of heat as a function of temperature.

Fig.5. SEM images of SVM 1: (a) in-plane microstructure and (b) cross-sectional microstructure

Fig. 5 shows the vanadium composite film microstructure and grain morphology of SVM 1 with a thickness of about 0.6μm. It was found from Fig. 5 (a) that large agglomerates were dispersed homogeneously in the composite film. With the vertical dip-coating process used in this study, we obtained a granular-layered type of grain structure in a cross-sectional view as shown in Fig. 5 (b) which may provide better conducting paths compared with the planar shear microstructure.

4 Conclusions and Outlook

The applicability of a molybdenum-doped vanadium composite compound to the cold starting enhancement of polymer electrolyte fuel cells was

investigated by experimental methods. The preparation of molybdenum-doped vanadium oxide was conducted via an aqueous sol-gel process using flat stainless steel plates as substrates.

The experimental results revealed that the composite thin films were mainly composed of various vanadium oxide compounds acted as negative temperature coefficient materials from -20°C to 80°C. Also, it was found that large agglomerates were dispersed homogeneously in the film and a granular-layered type of film structure, resulting in a more electrically conductive morphology compared with the planar shear microstructure.

In a representative parameter study, we observed that the molybdenum-doped vanadium oxide composite materials synthesized in this study have electrical resistances of negative temperature coefficient characteristics, which is of great importance for fuel cell applications at subzero temperatures. It was found that the composite thin films can be greatly utilized as a self-heating thermal source for cold start enhancement of fuel cell engines.

References

- [1] A.P. Ahmad, G.-H. Kim and D.G. Jeffrey “*PEM Fuel Cell Freeze and Rapid Startup Investigation Milestone Report*”. NREL/MP-540-38760, U.S. DOE, 2005.
- [2] J.P. Meyers “Fundamental issues in subzero PEMFC startup and operation”. *DOE Workshop on Fuel Cell Operation at Sub-Freezing Temperatures*, 2005.
- [3] S. Glenn “Automotive PEM Stack Freeze Requirements & Suggested Fundamental Studies”. *DOE Workshop on Fuel Cell Operation at Sub-Freezing Temperatures*, 2005.
- [4] W.-S. Sung, S.-G. Yoon and Y.-I. Song “Method for Cold Starting Fuel Cell Vehicles”. Hyundai Motor Company, US Patent Application Number 2011 0014534, 2011.
- [5] M. Imada, A. Fujimori, and Y. Tokura “Metal-insulator transitions”. *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, Vol. 70, No. 4, pp 1039-1263, 1998.
- [6] H. Futaki “A New Type Semiconductor (Critical Temperature Resistor)”. *Japanese J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp 28-41, 1965.
- [7] H. Futaki and A. Minoru “Effects of Various Doping Elements on the Transition Temperature of Vanadium Oxide Semiconductors”. *Japanese J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol. 8, No. 8, pp 1008-1013, 1969.
- [8] Z.P. Wu, A. Miyashita, S. Yamamoto, H. Abe, I. Nashiyama, K. Narumi “Molybdenum substitutional doping and its effects on phase transition properties in single crystalline vanadium dioxide thin film”. *J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol. 86, No. 9, pp 5311-5313, 1999.
- [9] G. Guzman, R. Morineau and J. Livage “Synthesis of vanadium dioxide thin films from vanadium alkoxides”. *Materials Research Bulletin*, Vol. 29, No. 5, pp 509-515, 1994.
- [10] D.P. Partlow, S.R. Gurkovich, K.C. Radford and L.J. Denes “Switchable vanadium oxide films by a sol-gel process”. *J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol. 70, No. 1, pp 443-452, 1991.